

SensApp

D3.4 First prototypes of climate chamber module and liquid handling module and specification for the automated system

Grant Agreement Number	829104
Project Name	Super-sensitive detection of Alzheimer's disease biomarkers in plasma by an innovative droplet split-and-stack approach
Project Acronym	SensApp
Start date of the project	2019/01/01
End date of the project	2022/06/30
Work package producing the document	WP3 – Design and micro-engineering of the super-sensor building blocks
Deliverable identifier	D3.4
Nature of deliverable	Demonstrator
Lead beneficiary	GIN
Contributors	GIN, VTT, CNR
Dissemination level	Public
Author(s)	Markku Käsäkoski, Sanna Uusitalo, Simonetta Grilli
Version	V1.0
Due date	Month 29 (31 st May 2021)

Contents

1. Climate chamber module	3
1.1 Concept for climate and temperature control	3
1.2 Integration of climate chamber and DSS dispensing module	5
2. Concept for liquid handling	5
3. Conclusions	6

Task 3.4 aims at developing the humidity and temperature-controlled climate chamber for DSS dispensing as well as for the incubation processes for assay automation. According to the project plan the target control for humidity is $\pm 1\%RH$ and for T is $\pm 0.5^{\circ}C$. The climate chamber incorporates the DSS three-layer system developed in tasks T3.1, T3.2 and T3.3 by CNR, VUB and VTT. For the automation of liquid handling, the project plans to dispense sample ($\sim 1\mu L$) and reagents ($\sim 1nL$) with coefficient of variation better than 1% and 5%, respectively.

The COVID emergency had a dramatic impact on the activities of Ginolis. At the remote meeting on the 14th December 2020 (see the minutes of the meeting) Markku Käsäkoski explained that Ginolis received a great number of orders for producing systems to be employed for COVID pandemic and suffered lack of personnel to be focused on SensApp activities. Moreover, on March 2021 Markku Käsäkoski informed the coordinator that Ginolis was acquired by Cellink, changing the SME status of Ginolis. As a direct consequence, the end month of this task has been postponed to M29 and, in order to speed up the activities, the requirements for the handling of reagent volumes have been lightened.

1. Climate chamber module

1.1. Concept for climate and temperature control

The aim of this task is to provide proper environmental conditions (humidity and temperature) for DSS and incubation protocols. Target humidity control was $\pm 1\%RH$ and for T $\pm 0.5^{\circ}C$. Climate chamber unit integrates the heater, temperature control, ultrasonic humidifier, humidity control, air flow control and climate chamber. There was no requirement to have dry air conditions during any of the processes and thus no drier was integrated. Ultrasonic humidifier is based on piezoceramic transducers, which are attached to the bottom of the fluid tank. During excitation of the transducer, the water leads the ultrasonic vibrations to the boundary layer between water and air. Constant compression and decompression of the water gauge over the transducer causes cavitation in the immediate proximity of the water surface. Thus, crossing capillary waves are developed, the finest water particles of which, the aerosols, are produced in the wave crest. The aerosols are delivered by the air flow in the humidifier and quickly mix with the ambient air. They have a small diameter ($\sim 0.001 - 0.005$ mm) and thus form a freely floating mist. The droplet diameter depends on the surface tension and the density of the medium, but also on the excitation frequency. The higher the excitation frequency, the smaller is the diameter of the droplets. It is optimal due to energy saving. Compared to steam and infrared humidifiers with the same humidification output, the ultrasonic humidifier needs up to 93 % less electricity.

Specifications for the climate and temperature control is that climate chamber size is 75L (50 cm x 50 cm x 50 cm), time to control humidity and temperature is better than 15 min (@ $30^{\circ}C$ and $80\%RH$). The outcomes from WP2 did not require specifications for temperature or humidity control precision, but typical achievable values are $\pm 1.0^{\circ}C$ and $\pm 3\%RH$. In order to humidify the required volume from $40\%RH$ to $80\%RH$ with temperature change $20^{\circ}C$ to $30^{\circ}C$, 25mL/h water is needed. Climate chamber has two chambers of which one is pre-chamber for humidified air ($>90\%RH$) and second is the actual climate chamber. Pre-chamber is heated, and the required heater power is min. 100W and it also has the ultrasonic humidifier and humidity regulator with hygostat. Humidity and temperature in the climate chamber are controlled with additional heater (min 20W) and proportional integral derivative (PID) controller and air blower (fan) with pulse width modulation (PWM) control. To reach the set temperature and humidity the simultaneous control would be fastest, but to reduce the risk of condensation of water temperature is controlled first and only then the

SensApp has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under agreement No 829104. www.sensapp.eu

humidity. Used T, P and %RH sensor is precision sensor BME280 from Bosch measuring humidity with $\pm 3\%$ accuracy, barometric pressure with ± 1 hPa absolute accuracy, and temperature with $\pm 1.0^\circ\text{C}$ accuracy.

Used components for climate chamber control are:

Ultrasonic humidifier	KMB (Boga GmbH)
Humidity regulator (hygrostat at pre-chamber)	BO-HG-M (Boga GmbH)
Controller	Raspberry Pi
Sensors (T, %RH and P)	BME280

Python was used as programming language and used libraries were Adafruit BME280 library, blinka, RPi.GPIO and guizero.

Software modules:

Main	SensAppMain.py
Setup of IO connections	Setup.py
PIDControl with parameter (P, I and D) setup	PIDControl.py
FanControl for air blower control	FanControl.py
Error situation handling	ErrorControl.py
Heater control	Heater.py
Humidifier control	Humidifier.py

The main module checks the sensor values in every 1s, checks the status of system and monitors whether the set value has been reached.

Schematics and layout for 5V fan connections and sensor connections are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic view of Raspberry Pi connections

1.2. Integration of Climate chamber and DSS dispensing module

The climate chamber and DSS dispensing unit have been designed so that they can be easily integrated at CNR laboratory. The DSS dispenser is an independent unit with power switch panel that can be customized

for the climate chamber with simple electronic connectors. The DSS dispenser is controlled through its own user interface. The climate chamber has a separate control system.

2. Concept for liquid handling

GIN provides here an automated robot to handle the samples between different chambers with controlled humidity and temperature. Figure 2 shows the flow of a typical protocol coming out from WP2 as a reference.

Step	N. Jet	Concentration	Volume	Condition	Incubation		
					Time	Humidity	Temperat.
1		50ug/ml 50ng/ml 500pg/ml					
2	20						
3				Static	2h	≈ 90%	25°C
4		blockIt buffer Arrayt	2ml	Static	3h	≈ 32%	25°C
5		dH2O	10ml	On shaker	5min x 3		25°C
6		1:1600	2ml	Static	18h	≈ 90%	4°C
7		dH2O	10ml	On shaker	5min x 3		25°C
8		0,5ug/ml	2ml	Static	1h	≈90%	25°C
9		dH2O	10ml	On shaker	5min x 3		25°C
10							

Figure 2. Flow of a typical reaction protocol coming out from WP2 as example.

Step 1 represents the manual preparation of the samples. The reaction slide is inserted in the DSS module manually. The operator takes the slide from the DSS module and places it into the incubator (Step 3). The liquid handling system is taking care of step 4 (dispensing the blocking buffer) and step 5 (washing). After step 5 the operator moves the slide to the refrigerator. After overnight incubation at refrigerator, the operator places the slide in the liquid handling module and steps 7 to 9 are performed in the liquid handling module. After final wash (step 9) the operator moves the slide to the reading unit manually.

Figure 3 shows the workflow for the semi-automated liquid handling system.

Figure 3. Liquid handling module workflow.

After sample incubation, the robotic arm brings the slide under the blocking buffer dispenser (peristaltic) and after dispensing the arm the robot brings it to incubation. After incubation, the robotic arm takes the slide for washing to the shaker and after 3 washing cycles the system takes the slide to the pick-up position and alarms the operator that the slide is ready to be moved to the refrigerator. The day after, the operator brings the slide to the pick-up position and the robot picks the slide and brings it to the secondary antibody dispensing position and after dispensing to the incubation. After incubation, the robot picks the slide and takes the slide for washing to the shaker and after 3 washing cycles the robot takes the slide to the pick-up position and alarms the operator that slide is ready to be moved to reader.

3. Conclusions

The integration of the climate chamber with DSS dispensing module and liquid handling module will be completed in WP4. In future, with more time available for testing, the slides will be equipped with regions delimited by hydrophobic barriers around the spot region and the liquid handling will be fully automated with lower reagent volumes. In this way the multiplexing of samples will be possible, and the amounts of buffers and reagents needed will be reduced. Also, by experience the washing quality can be improved and thus the background signal can be reduced. Most likely, the incubation times could be reduced.

Appendix 1: Software modules

SensAppMain.py

```

import Setup
import SensorControl
import time
import FanControl
import sys
import ErrorControl
import PIDControl
import RPi.GPIO as GPIO
from time import sleep
from datetime import datetime
from guizero import App, Text, TextBox, PushButton
import sys
import os

class State:
    def __init__(self):
        self.setup = self.Setup()
        self.run = False
        self.ready = True
        self.error = False
        self.startTime = datetime.now()
        self.endTime = None

class Setup:
    heating = True
    dehumidifying = True
    humidifying = True

    def humidify(self):
        """
        Control humidifier
        """
        pass

    def dehumidify(self):
        """
        Control dehumidifier
        """
        pass

    def CheckReady(self, temperature, humidity, temperatureSetPoint,
humiditySetPoint):
        if ((abs(temperature - temperatureSetPoint) < 0.2)
and (abs(humidity - humiditySetPoint) < 0.2)):
            self.ready = True
            self.endTime = datetime.now()
        else:
            self.ready = False

def heating():

```

```

pass

def CheckStartState(temperatureThreshold, data, error):
    error.TemperatureError.CheckTemperature(temperatureThreshold)
    error.DryError.CheckHumidity(10)
    error.HumidError.CheckHumidity(85)

def main():
    """
    Heater and heating needs to be either worked independently or
    somehow added to this code. As of now, the heater is just 0
    and heating / heater does nothing.
    """

    USAGE = 'usage: %s <humidity setpoint> <temperature setpoint>' %
sys.argv[0]
    try:
        humiditySetPoint = float(sys.argv[1])
        if humiditySetPoint < 0:
            humiditySetPoint = 0
        elif humiditySetPoint > 100:
            humiditySetPoint = 100
    except ValueError:
        print("\nStart the program by typing python3 SensAppMain.py humidity
setpoint temperature setpoint")
        print("\nBoth setpoints need to be numbers, for example, 80 % RH and
30 C should be inputed as")
        print("\npython3 SensAppMain.py 80 30")
    try:
        temperatureSetPoint = float(sys.argv[2])
    except ValueError:
        print("\nStart the program by typing python3 SensAppMain.py humidity
setpoint temperature setpoint")
        print("\nBoth setpoints need to be numbers, for example, 80 % RH and
30 C should be inputed as")
        print("\npython3 SensAppMain.py 80 30")

    def Reset():
        os.execl(sys.executable, sys.executable, *sys.argv)

    def Shutdown():
        sys.exit()

    def Update(errorState, sensorlist, data, systemState,
temperatureSetPoint, humiditySetPoint, fanlist):
        e = errorState.CheckErrors()
        if e == True:
            systemState.error = True
        else:
            systemState.error = False

    """
    The system state should be checked here for errors,

```

```

so that the system doesn't run on false information
"""
if systemState.ready == False and systemState.error == False:

    data.ReadSensors(sensorlist, list1, list2, list3)
    temperature = data.current.temperatureList[3]
    humidity = data.current.humidityList[3]

    systemState.CheckReady(temperature, humidity,
temperatureSetPoint, humiditySetPoint)
    if systemState.ready == True:
        readycheck.value = "Ready"
        print("\nReady")
        totalTime = str(systemState.endTime-systemState.startTime)
        timePrint = "\nRuntime {} min {} s".format(totalTime[2:4],
totalTime[5:7])
        print(timePrint)
    else:
        output, fan = PIDControl.PIDHumidity(humiditySetPoint, data,
systemState)
        FanControl.ChangeSpeed(fanlist, fan, output)

"""
These lines simply start the UI, it should be possible to
make a module out of these to make the code easier to read
but as of now it adds too many bugs
"""

app = App("SensApp", layout="grid")

humidSP = Text(app, text="Humidity setpoint", grid=[0,0])
tempSP = Text(app, text="Temperature setpoint", grid=[1,0])

sensor1 = Text(app, text="Sensor 1 values", grid=[0,3])
sensor2 = Text(app, text="Sensor 2 values", grid=[0,5])
sensor3 = Text(app, text="Sensor 3 values", grid=[0,7])
sensor4 = Text(app, text="Sensor 4 values", grid=[0,9])

temp1 = Text(app, text="0 C", grid=[0,4])
pressure1 = Text(app, text="0 hPa", grid=[1,4])
humid1 = Text(app, text="0 %", grid=[2,4])

temp2 = Text(app, text="0 C", grid=[0,6])
pressure2 = Text(app, text="0 hPa", grid=[1,6])
humid2 = Text(app, text="0 %", grid=[2,6])

temp3 = Text(app, text="0 C", grid=[0,8])
pressure3 = Text(app, text="0 hPa", grid=[1,8])
humid3 = Text(app, text="0 %", grid=[2,8])

temp4 = Text(app, text="0 C", grid=[0,10])
pressure4 = Text(app, text="0 hPa", grid=[1,10])
humid4 = Text(app, text="0 %", grid=[2,10])

readycheck = Text(app, text="Not ready", grid=[2,11])

hsp = "{:.1f} %".format(humiditySetPoint)

```

```

tsp = "{:.1f} C".format(temperatureSetPoint)
tempSP = Text(app, text=hsp, grid=[0,1])
humidSP = Text(app, text=tsp, grid=[1,1])

reset = PushButton(app, command=Reset, text="Reset", grid=[2,0])
quit = PushButton(app, command=Shutdown, text="Shutdown", grid=[3,0])

list1 = [temp1, temp2, temp3, temp4]
list2 = [pressure1, pressure2, pressure3, pressure4]
list3 = [humid1, humid2, humid3, humid4]

systemState = State()
systemState.ready = False
sensorList, fanList = Setup.SetupDevices(systemState)
data = SensorControl.data(list1, list2, list3)
heater = 0
errorState = ErrorControl.Error(sensorList, fanList, heater,
temperatureSetPoint, data, list1, list2, list3)

    app.repeat(1000, Update, args=[errorState, sensorList, data,
systemState, temperatureSetPoint, humiditySetPoint, fanList])
    #After this nothing happens unless the UI is closed, the display()
starts infinite loop
    app.display()

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()

```

```

SetUp.py

import RPi.GPIO as GPIO
import board
import busio
import digitalio
import adafruit_bme280
import SensAppMain

def SetupDevices(state):

    """
    Setup all devices
    """
    GPIO.setmode(GPIO.BCM)

    SensorList = SetupSensors(state)

    FanList = SetupFans()

    SetupHeater()

    return SensorList, FanList

def SetupSensors(state):

    cs1 = digitalio.DigitalInOut(board.D5)
    cs2 = digitalio.DigitalInOut(board.D6)
    cs3 = digitalio.DigitalInOut(board.D0)
    cs4 = digitalio.DigitalInOut(board.D22)

    sensorList = []

    sensorList.append(SetupSensor(cs1, 0, state))
    sensorList.append(SetupSensor(cs2, 1, state))
    sensorList.append(SetupSensor(cs3, 2, state))
    sensorList.append(SetupSensor(cs4, 3, state))

    return sensorList

def SetupFans():

    pin1 = 12
    pin2 = 13

    GPIO.setup(pin1, GPIO.OUT)
    GPIO.setup(pin2, GPIO.OUT)

    try:
        p1 = GPIO.PWM(pin1, 50)
        p2 = GPIO.PWM(pin2, 50)
        FanList = [p1, p2]
        return FanList
    except RuntimeError:
        print("\nFans already set up")
        return [0,0]

```

```
def SetupHeater():
    #Placeholder
    pass

def SetupSensor(cs, num, state):
    spi = busio.SPI(board.SCK, MOSI=board.MOSI, MISO=board.MISO)
    try:
        sensor = adafruit_bme280.Adafruit_BME280_SPI(spi, cs)
        return sensor
    except RuntimeError:
        n = num+1
        print("\nSomething went wrong with sensor %d " %n)
        state.error = True
        return -1

def SetupFan(pin):
    GPIO.setup(pin1, GPIO.out)

    p = GPIO.PWM(50)

    return p
```

```

PIDControl.py

import SensorControl
import SensAppMain

values = {
    "accErrorTemp": [0,0,0,0],
    "accErrorHumid": 0
}

def PIDHumidity(sp, data, state):

    """
    These values are only preliminary and may not work
    Test with usual PID tuning methods
    """
    P = 0.2
    I = 0.001
    D = 0.05

    humidityCurr = data.current.temperatureList[3]
    humidityPrev = data.previous.humidityList[3]

    if abs(humidityCurr-sp) < 1:
        state.ready = True
        return 0

    error = sp - humidityCurr
    values["accErrorHumid"] += error

    proportional = error * P

    integral = values["accErrorHumid"] * I

    derivative = (humidityCurr - humidityPrev) * D

    output = proportional + integral + derivative

    if output > 100:
        output = 100
    elif output < 0:
        output = 0

    if humidityCurr < sp:
        fan = 0
    else:
        fan = 1

    return output, fan

def PIDTemperature(sp, data, state):

    """
    These values are only preliminary and may not work
    Test with usual PID tuning methods

```

```

"""

P = 0.2
I = 0.001
D = 0.05

tempListCurr = data.current.temperature

counter = 0
for i in range(4):
    if abs(tempListCurr-sp) < 0.1:
        counter += 1
if counter == 4:
    return 0

errorList = []
proportionalList = []
derivativeList = []
integralList = []
output = []

for i in range(4):
    errorList.append(sp - tempListCurr[i])
    proportionalList.append(errorList[i] * P)

    values["accErrorTemp"][i] += error
    integralList.append(values["accErrorTemp"][i] * I)

    derivativeList.append((tempListCurr[i]-tempListPrev[i]) * D)

    output.append(proportionalList[i] + integralList[i] +
derivativeList[i])
    if output[i] > 100:
        output[i] = 100
    elif output[i] < 0:
        output[i] = 0
return output

```

ErrorControl.py

```

import RPi.GPIO as GPIO
import board
import busio
import adafruit_bme280
import digitalio
import SensAppMain
import SensorControl
import Setup
from time import sleep

class Error:

    """

    Class for errors and functions that determine error state.

    """

    def __init__(self, sensorList, fanList, heater, setPointTemp, data,
list1, list2, list3):
        self.sensorList = sensorList
        self.fanList = fanList
        self.heater = heater
        self.setPointTemp = setPointTemp
        self.data = data
        self.list1 = list1
        self.list2 = list2
        self.list3 = list3

        tempList = self.data.current.temperatureList
        humidityDry = self.data.current.humidityList[0]
        humidityHumid = self.data.current.humidityList[1]

        self.Sensor = self.SensorError(self.sensorList)
        self.Fan = self.FanError(self.fanList)
        self.Heater = self.HeaterError(0)
        self.Temperature = self.TemperatureError(tempList,
self.setPointTemp)
        self.Dry = self.DryError(humidityDry)
        self.Humid = self.HumidError(humidityHumid)
        self.CheckErrors()

    def CheckErrors(self):

        fl = self.fanList
        tl = self.data.current.temperatureList
        self.Sensor.CheckSensors()
        self.Fan.CheckFanError()
        self.Heater.CheckHeater()
        """

```

Reading the sensor from here will result in a bug where

the GUI will not update, so the reading has to come from the main module

```

"""
#self.data.ReadSensors(self.sensorList, self.list1, self.list2,
self.list3)

#self.TemperatureError.ChangeTemperature(self.Temperature, t1)
self.Dry.ChangeHumidity(self.data.current.humidityList[0])
self.Dry.CheckHumidity(10)
self.Humid.ChangeHumidity(self.data.current.humidityList[1])
self.Humid.CheckHumidity(85)

"""

This will determine whether the system is in error state or not
the function returns True, if it is in error state, and False
if it is not
This is used in the main module state to keep the system from
operating
under error conditions

Uncomment the lines to add these errors to error state
"""
if True in self.Sensor.sensorError:
    return True
elif True in self.Fan.fanError:
    return True
#elif self.Heater.heaterError == True:
#    return True
#elif True in self.Temperature.tempError:
#    return True
#elif self.Dry.error == True:
#    return True
#elif self.Humid.error == True:
#    return True
#else:
#    return False

class SensorError:
    """
    Check sensors for problems, very rarely the sensor may end up in a
    error state, where the data from register is not available. Should
    not
    happen in use if set up properly, but has happened once
    """
    def __init__(self, sensorList):
        self.sensorError = [False, False, False, False]
        self.sensorList = sensorList
        self.CheckSensors()

    def CheckSensors(self):
        for i in range(4):
            #print(self.sensorError)
            try:
                temp = self.sensorList[i].temperature
                self.sensorError[i] = False

```

```

except AttributeError:
    num = i+1
    print("\nSensor %d not set properly" %num)
    self.sensorError[i] = True
"""
Can be used with RuntimeError, but AttributeError should
find the error, and this has sometimes caused bugs
where the data isn't shown properly

except RuntimeError:
    num = i+1
    print("\nSensor %d not set properly" %num)
    self.sensorError[i] = True
"""

```

```
class FanError:
```

```

def __init__(self, fanList):
    self.fanList = fanList
    self.fanError = [False, False]
    self.CheckFanError()

def CheckFanError(self):
    """
    Figure out how to determine error with fans
    The code itself doesn't give any errors when using fans
    even if they are not working. Maybe use camera or something
    to see if the fan is running or not
    """
    pass

```

```
class HeaterError:
```

```

def __init__(self, heater):
    self.heater = heater
    self.heaterError = False
    self.CheckHeater()

def CheckHeater(self):
    """
    Check errors with heater
    """
    pass

```

```
class TemperatureError:
```

```
    """
```

First initiate object that has list of possible error states and a list of temperatures in the system. If temperature changes in the system, the list can be updated with ChangeTemperature, as setpoint can be updated if necessary with ChangeSetPoint

CheckTemperature goes through the list and checks every temperature to see if there is too great difference in temperature between setpoint and current temperature.

Basically the idea is to keep the system from being too cold, to not
 let water condense

```

"""
def __init__(self, tempList, setpoint):
    self.tempList = tempList
    self.tempError = [False, False, False, False]
    self.tempSetPoint = setpoint
    self.CheckTemperature(self.tempSetPoint)

def ChangeTemperature(self, tempList):
    self.tempList = tempList
    self.CheckTemperature(self.tempSetPoint)

def ChangeSetPoint(self, setpoint):
    self.tempSetPoint = setpoint
    self.CheckTemperature(self.tempSetPoint)

def CheckTemperature(self, temp):
    for i in range(4):
        if abs(self.tempList[i]-temp) > 0.2:
            self.tempError[i] = True
        else:
            self.tempError[i] = False

```

```

class DryError:
    """
    Object for testing the dry vault for too high humidity,
    basically the air flow from dry vault should be as dry as possible
    """

```

```

def __init__(self, humidity):
    self.humidity = humidity
    self.error = False
    self.CheckHumidity(10)

def ChangeHumidity(self, humidity):
    self.humidity = humidity
    self.CheckHumidity(10)

def CheckHumidity(self, setpoint):
    if self.humidity > setpoint:
        self.error = True
    else:
        self.error = False

```

```

class HumidError:
    """
    Object for testing the humid vault for too low humidity,
    basically the air flow from humid vault should be as humid as
    possible,
    but not over 90 % as that may cause problems with fans
    """

```

```

def __init__(self, humidity):
    self.humidity = humidity
    self.error = False

```

```
self.CheckHumidity(85)

def ChangeHumidity(self, humidity):
    self.humidity = humidity
    self.CheckHumidity(85)

def CheckHumidity(self, setpoint):
    if self.humidity < setpoint:
        self.error = True
    else:
        self.error = False
```

